

CURRENT CHALLENGES IN IMPORT SUBSTITUTION IN THE NATIONAL ECONOMY OF AZERBAIJAN

Rafizade I.

UNEC, PHD Candidate, Azerbaijan

Abstract

This paper explores the challenges and strategies of import substitution in Azerbaijan's economy, highlighting its role in promoting domestic production and reducing dependence on imports. The analysis covers government policies, technological needs, inflation control, and global trade dynamics. It finds that while Azerbaijan has made progress in diversifying its economy and fostering local industries, significant efforts in R&D, regional development, and policy adaptation are essential for sustained success. The study concludes that a well-executed import substitution strategy can enhance economic resilience, but it requires comprehensive planning, continuous evaluation, and investment in innovation and infrastructure.

Keywords: Import substitution, economic resilience, domestic production, non-oil sector development, technology transfer and innovation.

Introduction:

Import substitution has long been regarded as a strategic pillar in the development policies of nations aiming to build a resilient and self-sufficient economy. This approach focuses on fostering local production capabilities to meet domestic demand, thereby diminishing reliance on imports and enhancing the country's economic resilience. For Azerbaijan, which possesses a rich array of natural and economic resources, import substitution has emerged as an essential component of its economic policy framework aimed at reducing vulnerability to global market fluctuations and promoting sustainable growth.

Expanded Analysis on Import Substitution in Azerbaijan:

Economic Context and Strategic Importance:

Import substitution in Azerbaijan is not just an economic policy but an integrated part of the national development agenda. The strategy aims to shift from a reliance on imports, particularly in the non-oil sector, to fostering a diversified economic base that can sustain growth and create employment. The "Azerbaijan 2030: National Priorities for Socio-Economic Development," approved by presidential decree in 2021, underscores

the importance of developing local production capabilities to achieve a resilient, competitive economy. The document outlines a multi-faceted approach that includes enhancing industrial infrastructure, advancing technological capabilities, and building human capital.

Challenges and Strategic Goals: A critical challenge facing Azerbaijan's import substitution strategy is the modernization of its industrial sector to enable it to compete effectively with foreign imports. While the country has significant resource potential, leveraging it efficiently requires substantial investments in R&D, technology transfer, and innovation adoption. Ensuring that local industries have access to cutting-edge technologies and fostering an ecosystem that supports innovation are essential steps to producing high-quality, competitively priced goods.

Azerbaijan's manufacturing sector has shown mixed performance over the past decade. From 2013 to 2022, the share of production in the manufacturing sector decreased from 21.4% to 21%. However, this period also saw peaks, notably in 2015 and 2020, indicating that targeted measures for promoting local production and import substitution during economic downturns yielded positive results.

Graph 1. Sectoral Structure of Industrial Production, as a Percentage of the Total, Based on Actual Prices of Respective Years

**Source: Compiled by the author based on data obtained from the State Statistics Committee website https://www.stat.gov.az/source/food_balances/ (as of 19.02.2023) **

Government Policies and Legislative Support:

The government's support for import substitution has been multifaceted, encompassing legislative initiatives, financial incentives, and strategic partnerships. Key policies have included tax incentives for local manufacturers, subsidies for R&D initiatives, and strategic investments in critical sectors such as agriculture, pharmaceuticals, and light manufacturing. The State Program for Industry Development and various regional development plans also emphasize the need to strengthen local production capabilities and promote diversification.

Impact of Global Trade Dynamics: The global economic environment and international trade agreements play a significant role in shaping Azerbaijan's import substitution strategies. Balancing these strategies with the country's international trade obligations is crucial to avoid trade conflicts and maintain a competitive position in global markets. The shift in Azerbaijan's main import partners over the years reflects its adaptive

approach to global trade dynamics. For example, while Russia, the United Kingdom, and Singapore were key import sources in 2005, by 2022, the focus had shifted towards Russia, Turkey, China, Germany, and other regional players. This shift indicates an effort to diversify partnerships and secure trade routes that support the country's import substitution goals.

Detailed Economic Analysis:

Inflation Trends and Price Competitiveness:

Managing inflation and ensuring price competitiveness are vital for a successful import substitution policy. In July 2022, inflation in Azerbaijan stood at 12.7%, which slightly reduced to 12.2% by July 2023. Food inflation also declined from 15.1% to 14.3% during the same period. A significant decrease was observed in producer prices, which fell by 15.5%. Meanwhile, import price indices were measured at 123.4 and 127.9 points, indicating that domestic production is becoming more cost-effective compared to imported goods.

Graph 2. Dynamics of Prices for Products of Azerbaijani Producers

Source: <https://tradingeconomics.com/azerbaijan> and data from the Central Bank of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

Lower domestic production costs can enhance local producers' ability to meet domestic demand, reduce reliance on foreign suppliers, and encourage consumer preference for local products. This shift not only strengthens the economic stability of the nation but also stimulates job creation and technological advancement within the local economy.

Amid measures aimed at curbing inflation and reducing prices, Trading Economics' global macro models and analysts' expectations predict that by the end of the third quarter of 2023, producer prices in Azerbaijan are expected to change by -4.00% (<https://tradingeconomics.com/azerbaijan/forecast>).

Regional Implications and Future Outlook: Implementing an effective import substitution policy also requires regional development. Azerbaijan's varied regions have different resource bases, industrial capacities, and levels of technological advancement. A targeted approach that leverages these regional differences by fostering specialized industrial zones and innovation hubs is essential for maximizing the potential of import substitution strategies. For instance, the establishment of industrial parks and free economic

zones in areas like Sumgayit and Ganja has played a role in boosting local production.

The future success of Azerbaijan's import substitution efforts will hinge on continuous adaptation to new economic realities, investments in human capital to develop skilled labor, and maintaining a balance between local and global market demands. The medium-term focus (3-5 years) should prioritize strengthening research institutions, enhancing industry-academia collaboration, and developing sustainable practices that can support long-term economic growth.

Conclusion:

Import substitution in Azerbaijan is an evolving strategy that integrates national policy objectives with broader socio-economic goals. While the country has made strides in creating a more self-sufficient economy, challenges such as technological modernization, infrastructure development, and the need for continuous policy adaptation remain. The effectiveness of these policies will depend on their implementation and the country's ability to respond to global economic changes. With a strategic approach and concerted efforts across all sectors, Azerbaijan can build a resilient,

competitive economy that supports long-term sustainable growth.

References

1. Nadirov, A.A., et al. (2003). *Economic Resource Potential in Azerbaijan: Opportunities and Challenges*. Baku: Azerbaijan State Economic University Press.
2. Azerbaijan State Statistics Committee (2022). *Annual Economic Report*. Available at: <https://www.stat.gov.az>
3. Trading Economics (2023). *Azerbaijan Producer Prices Forecast*. Available at: <https://tradingeconomics.com/azerbaijan/forecast>
4. President of the Republic of Azerbaijan (2021). *Azerbaijan 2030: National Priorities for Socio-Economic Development*. Presidential Decree, Baku.
5. Central Bank of Azerbaijan (2022). *Inflation and Economic Indicators Report*. Available at: <https://www.cbar.az>
6. Ministry of Economy of the Republic of Azerbaijan (2022). *Import Substitution and Industrial Policy Overview*.
7. World Bank (2023). *Economic Indicators and Analysis: Azerbaijan*. Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/azerbaijan>
8. International Monetary Fund (2022). *Azerbaijan Country Report*. Washington, D.C.: IMF Publishing.